

Code Editor Visual Editor Switch to PDF

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File outline

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1 [00:00:00]
2
3 R: Ok. And you do Artificial Intelligence, right? Or Computing Science?
4 S: Artificial Intelligence.
5 R: Which programming courses have you had?
6 S: Programming 1 and 2.
7 R: 1 and 2. And that was in Python?
8 S: Java. And right now it's... [mumbles incomprehensibly]
9 R: And in Russia, did you do anything?
10 S: I did data structures and algorithms, and introduction to programming which was using, like a local language developed there.
11 R: Ok, interesting.
12 S: Oh actually, I don't know if you know it, it's EIFFEL.
13 R: No, I don't know it actually. Ok, and the data structures, that was also programming or just theory?
14 S: In Java.
15
16 [00:01:13]
17
18 R: In Java as well, so you have some experience in Java.
19
20 [BEGIN TASK 34a]
21 R: Ok, great. Let's have a start with... Ok, we start with the first code-reading. This is the code and this is the instructions, so this is what I would like you to do. The idea is to describe the purpose of the code.
22 S: Ok. Ehm... Should I...?
23 R: Yeah, tell me what you think, when you look at the code, what you see.
24 S: Should I, like, describe while reading?
25 R: Yeah, please do.
26 S: So there's an array of rainValues, the current one is the first one, and for each valuing goes rainValues. If the current one, if the current one in the loop is less than, less than the current variable, the current becomes the one in the loop. And in the end the current one is printed so the current in the end is gonna be the least one of them, of the rainValues.
27 [END TASK 34a]
28 [00:02:43]
29
30 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34a]
31 R: Ok, good. And if you would give the function a name, how would you call it?
32 S: Ehm, minrainvalues.
33 R: Ok, can you type that in here, what would you call the function?
34 S: [types "minRainValue"]
35
36 [00:03:00]
37
38 R: Ok, now I wanna ask you a few small, short questions about the task that you've just done. The code, if you have a look at the code, how complex do you find the code? Like the algorithm itself, do you find it easy or complex on the scale from 0 to 10, zero meaning it was the easiest, and ten that it was the most complex. So it's about the algorithm itself.
39 S: I'd say maybe 4.
40
41 [00:03:36]
42
43 R: Ok, now the task covered concepts and definitions that are perceived as very complex. The concepts you see here, there's a, you saw a for-loop, a for-each-loop, there's an array, there's an index, things like that are the concepts. How difficult did you find those?
44 S: Ehm... Well, I think, for my classes I guess just because the for-each which is taught, like, later. I guess I would give it like a, a... Ehm... I guess a four.
45
46 [00:04:30]
47
48 R: Ok, and then the last question about this. The instructions, I explained what you had to do, was it clear what I wanted you to do?
49 S: Yeah.
50
51 [00:04:43]
52
53 R: Ok, so, this is clear and that's not.
54
55 [END DISCUSS TASK 34a]
56 [BEGIN TASK 34b]
57 R: All right, now we will go on to the next one. Another code-reading question.
58 S: Ok. So there's an array of rainValues, the current one starts being the first one, and there's i which I suppose it's an iterator, so... while i is less than the length of the rainValues array, you compare the element at index i if it's, ehm... if it's greater than the current one you replace it, and you increase i in every iteration of the loop. And so in the end you're gonna print the, the biggest element of the rainValues array.
59 [END TASK 34b]
60 [00:05:52]
61 [DISCUSS TASK 34b]
62 R: Ok. Now we go back to the... Here you can type in what you think...
63 S: [types "maxRainValue"]
64
65 [00:06:07]
66
67 R: Perfect. Ok, and the programme code that you see there, how difficult do you find that, how complex?
68 S: Hm...
69 R: so the algorithm.
70 S: I'd say...
71 R: The fact that you have the iterator.
72 S: I guess 6.
73 R: What makes this one harder than the one before?
74 S: Yeah the iterator, I guess like, in the whole condition for the while, it takes a while to know that it's gonna go through all the elements and the current one will, will change.
75
76 [00:06:53]
77
78 R: Ok, and the concepts and definitions? So you see a while-loop, you see an if-loop, there's an array...
79 S: I'd say 5.
80
81 [00:07:12]
82
83 R: All right. And was it clear what you were supposed to do? Oh I messed up, I were very unclear, if it's not the case then it's easy. Should we go back and fix the last one, sorry, do you want to go back and fix the last one? What would you like to say for the first one? 1, and this one is a 0 or a 1?
84 S: A 0.

```

Track changes is off

You: S1 construct familiarity
Jan 10, 2024 11:44 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S6 WHILE harder/dispersed/error prone than FOR
Jan 10, 2024 11:15 AM • Edit

Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

85 [END DISCUSS TASK 34a]
86 [00:07:43]
87 [START TASK 34c]
88
89 R: Ok. All right, perfect. The last code-reading.
90 S: So there's again the array of rainValues. You have a counter and in a for-loop you iterate through all the values of the array and if one of them is zero you, you increase the counter. So in the end you're gonna print the counter of how many zero values are there in the, the rainValues.
91 [END TASK 34c]
92 [00:08:27]
93 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 34c]
94 R: Ok, how would you call the function? How would you summarize it?
95 S: Ehm... [types "countZeros"]
96
97 [00:08:45]
98
99 R: Yeah, all right. Ok, the programme code that you see here, how difficult did you find it to figure out what it did?
100 S: I'd say maybe 5.
101
102 [00:09:07]
103 [DISCUSS AND COMPARE FIRST THREE TASKS]
104 R: Ok, and the concepts and definitions? So this one has a different for-loop and a counter, and an index.
105 S: Ehm... For me it's easier to take the iterator directly from the for-loop instead of having it like, outside.
106 R: What do you mean?
107 S: Like, to define the iterator inside the for-loop.
108 R: So you have, like, you find this easier than...
109 S: Than to define the...
110 R: Like you had it in a while, you mean.
111 S: Yeah.
112 R: Yeah. So if you have here, this is the for-each and this is the while-loop and this is the for. which one do you find the easiest?
113 S: Well, I guess... This one, because this is like more messy for me to, like you define the i but you only use it inside the loop, so for this code you don't really need it in another place. And, and, well, yeah, between the for-loops I guess it could depend on the occasion.
114 R: Yeah, but if you read it, which one do you feel most comfortable with?
115 S: I'd say the for-each.
116 R: Because?
117 S: Because it's easier to read, like, you just say for each value in values...
118 R: Ok, and is it, even though you didn't learn it until later, because you said I've, I have less experience with this it's still, that's ok? So you say once you learn it it's fine, then it's easier to use.
119 S: Yeah, I think it was easier because it's easier to, to read it straight away.
120
121 [00:11:15]
122 [CONT. DISCUSS TASK 34c]
123 R: Ok. Ehm... The concepts and definitions, so this for-loop, how difficult, how complex do you find this?
124 S: Hm.. Maybe also a 5. [silence for 10 seconds]
125 R: why are you...?
126 S: I don't know which should be my reference, like, what's the...
127 R: Oh, compared to each other, yeah, ok, I understand. We're gonna order these later anyway. So if you just think of the first thing you think of is a 5, then just put the 5. If that's what you...
128
129 [00:11:57]
130
131 R: And how clear were the instructions, did you know what you had to do?
132
133 [00:12:02]
134 [CONT. DISCUSS COMPARE FIRST THREE TASKS]
135
136 R: Ok, now if you would organise these from most complex to most simple, how would you do that? You order them, or are they all just as hard, or is the one harder than the other?
137 S: I think I'm gonna put this one as the most complex because, yeah, like after knowing that you can arrange this one into a for-loop, yeah it just messes up, like, it messes up, like what am I gonna do with this value [refers to increment i]. And then...
138 R: This one you're like, because it's altogether, what it does with the index it's all in one line, yeah.
139 S: Ehm...
140 R: Yeah, the for-each was what you said before, you find that one easy because it's easy to read, it's just, yeah, ok. We're gonna put them in order like this, and then we have the most difficult on top. Ok, thank you. Ehm... I'm gonna make the screen a little bit bigger... Ok.
141
142 [END FIRST THREE TASKS]
143 [00:13:11]
144
145 R: Ehm, now I'm gonna ask you to write some code. Here's the task, but I'm not interested in what the syntax is, I'm gonna ask you not to press the run button. So I just wanna know, how would you attempt it and how are you going to do it, don't run it, I don't care if you make syntax mistakes. that's not my interest. Ok? So read the question and we'll see.
146
147 [00:13:36]
148
149 [BEGIN TASK 81: MAX FREQ]
150 S: [silence for 15 seconds] Ok.
151
152 [00:13:52]
153
154 R: So what's your plan, what do you wanna do?
155 S: Ehm, I guess we have to calculate first the maximum, and then count how many times it happened. Hmm... [silence for 5 seconds] Yeah, it can be like, I guess it can be separated, like first a loop to check the, the maximum, then the counter, or maybe it can be inside the same loop. Ehm... Yeah I guess it could be easier to put it inside the same loop. So should I...?
156 R: Yeah, go ahead.
157 S: So I'm gonna create a counter, which starts at zero, then we have a for-loop
158 R: Are the keys in a different place? Do you have a Spanish keyboard at home?
159 S: Yep. Oh... rainValues.length... And... Ok. So... Ehm... I'm also gonna check the current one. It's... biggest... choose the first one. Ehm... So if, if this one is bigger than the biggest, if [silence for 10 seconds] then... Oh. If the current one is bigger than the biggest, then you... [silence for 15 seconds]
160 R: What are you thinking about?
161 S: Because then I want to compare if it's the same to increase the, the counter. Can I copy-paste[refers to own line of code]?
162 R: Yeah, sure.
163 S: So if it's the same as the biggest, you just increase the counter. And then that means that the first, the counter has started in 1. Ehm... But if you find a bigger one, you reset the count to 1. And you increase the biggest... [silence for 13 seconds] Ehm... So, let me just check if this is working... Ehm... So it's starting 25 so let's say that's the biggest, and then you go to 70, now that's the biggest one, counter is gonna be 1, then it's the same so it's gonna increase, it's gonna increase, and then it finds a bigger one, so it restarts the counter to 1, then it increases and it does nothing, does nothing... and in the end it would just print. [silence for 15 seconds] Print the... the count. Yep.
164 [END TASK 81: MAX FREQ]
165 [00:14:52]

You: S6 WHILE harder/dispersed/error prone than FOR
Jan 10, 2024 11:16 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: S8 FOREACH overzichtelijk/compact
Jan 10, 2024 11:17 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

Jan 10, 2024 11:20 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: S25 simultaneous tasks
Jan 10, 2024 11:21 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: S13 integrating multiple plans/merging harder
Jan 10, 2024 11:22 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O6 considers/knows construct - plan combo
Jan 10, 2024 11:22 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O10 minor forget&recall
Jan 10, 2024 11:23 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply
Resolve Reply

You: O7 tangled/patchwork
Jan 10, 2024 11:23 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

165 [00:19:30]
166 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 81]
167 R: All right, good. And, ok, if you look at your program code and compare it to the things you've seen before in the reading questions, how much is this easier, more complex or less complex than you've seen? How complex would you...?
168 S: Hmm... I don't remember which one I gave the most... Maybe it would be like a... But complexity like, in comparison to... maybe like a full programme or...?
169 R: Yeah or compared to what you've seen now, yeah.
170 S: I'd say 7.
171 R: Ok, so you found it more complex than what you've seen there.
172 S: Yeah, because I, there were more tasks and the combining of the two of them in the same array, same loop, made it more complex.
173
174 [00:21:03]
175
176 R: Ok. And the concepts and definitions that you've used?
177 S: Well it was the counter, iterator was inside the for-loops, so it was easier for me. And it was just the counter and the replacing of the biggest, so I'll say 6.
178
179 [00:21:29]
180
181 R: Ok. And did you know what you have to do, were the instructions clear? Ok, now this is the task that you did, how many days is the maximum, where would you order that? We said most difficult was on top. All right, ok. Awesome, you did a good job!
182 [END DISCUSS TASK 81]
183
184 [00:22:01]
185 [BEGIN TASK 83b]
186 R: Yeah, go ahead.
187 S: [silence for 50 seconds]
188 R: What are you thinking about?
189 S: I'm trying to understand it.
190 R: What you have to do?
191 S: Yeah. So I guess the first rainy day would be the first nonzero value in the array, starting from the left. And the last, last rainy day would be the last, nonzero value in the array. Ok, so I can use, ehm... I need an iterator to keep track of the index. I can... Maybe a while, so while the element at index i is zero, you keep increasing. Oh, I just... Ok, so, I want to use a while, and I need to find the iterator outside. [silence for 10 seconds] So while the value at index i is equal to, no... Yeah, is equal to zero. You increase i, so I'd say there's two zeroes in here, it would increase and increase... Ok. Try... Oh.
192 R: What did you forget about?
193 S: The error message. Should I print the, both these in the same?
194 R: Oh, that doesn't matter, however you want.
195 S: Ehm... Because right now I already have the, the start, hmm... So I'm gonna... Can I assume there's a print method?
196 R: Yeah, if you want you can copy it from here. It's system.out.println.
197 S: So now what you see, is the...
198 R: Oh, yeah. Ok, that's where you... Ok.
199 S: All right, so now, I would say, hmm... The first one is ehm... The i. No. Before that I should check the... for the error message. So if the, if it found no rain, rainy days, it means that, that the... Yeah, no. So if the first one is zero, i is gonna be... I'm confused.
200 R: You're doing good!
201 S: It's gonna be a null-pointer exception. [silence for 7 seconds] If it doesn't find it at the first position it continues, so if you're here, continues and it checks but there's no limit in there so it's gonna be an exception. But... [silence for 18 seconds] I'm gonna use a for-loop?
202 R: Why do you wanna use a for-loop?
203 S: So that it stops when it... It stops before there's an exception, but it increments the i in the end. So while, i is just then... rainValues.length... [silence for 12 seconds] But then it doesn't make sense.
204 R: What are you trying to do?
205 S: To get the first nonzero element. Hmm... But if it doesn't find anything to know that it doesn't find... [silence for 14 seconds] Hmm... Because changing it for the for-loop gives me that number but it now doesn't make sense because there's nothing inside the for-loop. [silence for 7 seconds] oh yeah, yeah... Oh no... How can I change it to have a while-loop there?
206 R: Just keep going.
207 S: So while it's zero, and... And i is then... Is in the length... [silence for 7 seconds] So in that case if i is greater than the length... No. [silence for 12 seconds] That means it didn't find anything. So... And if it found something, then I can look for the, for the last day. Now, to look for the last day, I need to find... Hmm... Maybe I need the variable... to start the... Day... which would be equal to i. So you keep it here and until the end it's, if the index is not zero, you replace it, you replace the last day. [silence for 25 seconds] So while i is used then here... [silence for 15 seconds] Ehm... If the current element... is smaller than zero... then you replace the last... I don't know if I'll get rainy days on this. If you really could... If, til you find first the, first nonzero element, if it doesn't find anything it means it went to the end and so it prints an error message, but in the other case it means that it found the first day. Prints it, then there's a variable toward the last one, which would be this one, and so it checks again until the end to see if it's still greater than zero it means that it's the last day, and so it ends up with this one. And it should... [silence for 20 seconds] I think I missed it...
208 [END TASK 83b]
209 [00:36:40]
210 [BEGIN DISCUSS 83b]
211 R: All right, ok. let's have a... The first and the last rainy days. If you look at the code that you wrote, how complex would you consider that to be? Ok, and what makes it more complex than we've seen until now?
212 S: Well... Compared to the last one, now I needed to take into account the, the error message, and now you have to check for two days, so the first one affects the second one, and yeah, choosing between the while and the for-loop also confused me. Hmm...
213 R: And when you say you had to check for two days, is it the variables that you have to remember that's confusing, or the task that you think of, oh I have to go through it and look for the first day and I also have to do something else, I also have to go look for the last day?
214 S: Hmm... Yeah, like, if I'm gonna use the same variable, to to, like... If I'm gonna use an iterator, then it means that after checking the first day I still need to use that one so... It was kind of strange to...
215 R: Because you reused, because you were reusing it [the iterator]? Yeah, because here you also chose to start the last, the last day starts at i, why did you do that?
216 S: Hmm... Well, because it needs to be after the first day. So...
217 R: So, for efficiency? Also you can just walk through.
218 S: Oh yeah. I guess it's the same effect if you start it at zero, but... But yeah, I guess just.
219
220 [00:39:01]
221
222 R: This is smarter. It's because you don't really, you go through less, less things.
223 R: Ok, all right, the concepts and definitions, and the concepts that you used in the code, how complex do you find that?
224 S: [mumbles incomprehensibly]
225 R: You have troubles remembering what [method?] you did, something like that.
226 S: Because the concepts, I guess...
227
228 [00:39:27]
229
230 R: How would you order it?
231 S: This one...
232 R: Ok, and what made this one much more difficult than the one before? The one before was finding the maximum, so you said you walked through an array, counted...
233 S: I guess it was the interaction between the variables and choosing which control structure over the the use I want

Resolve Reply

You: O6 considers/knows construct-plan combo
Jan 10, 2024 11:22 AM • Edit
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You: O10 minor forget/recall
Jan 10, 2024 11:23 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: O7 tangled/patchwork
Jan 10, 2024 11:23 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O3 lacking terminate plan
Jan 11, 2024 5:14 PM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: O8 switches construct halfway
Jan 10, 2024 11:24 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: O8 switches construct halfway
Jan 10, 2024 11:25 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: O7 tangled/patchwork
Jan 10, 2024 11:26 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S21 unconfident reasoning about control flow
Jan 10, 2024 11:26 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S25 simultaneous tasks
Jan 10, 2024 11:27 AM • Edit
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Resolve Reply

You: S23 vars with multiple roles / re-use
Jan 10, 2024 11:27 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O9 considers efficiency
Jan 10, 2024 11:28 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S22 unclear intent/ambiguity

232 S: I guess it was the interaction between the variables, and choosing which control structure gave me, the use I want.

234 R: Yeah, ok. And, because you said before that you found the for-loop easier than the while, right? Because you, here you have the for-loop, the while you found more difficult than the for-loop. But when you started, you immediately started with the while, then you went to for and you came back to the while. Why, what was your reason for choosing a while?

235 S: I guess then, like, in this case, I would prefer a for-loop over the while because it's easier to imagine in my head, but once I was writing like, the first days here to, to choose right away was the while, because for the for-loop you need to, to maybe think more about, what are your, what is your initial variable, what is the iterator, and what's your condition, and how are you gonna use it?

236 R: And how are you gonna use it, the iterator or the condition?

237 S: Yeah because, well, when I changed it to the for-loop, I had the condition and the iteration, but, but then I didn't know what I was trying to do because maybe I was imagining it for a while, I don't know...

238 R: Yeah, you got confused there, like, ok let's go back. Fine, ok. Ehm, the concepts you used, you want to have a look back...

239 S: I think for the concepts I would say...

240 R: You said a 6, yeah. Last one was 6. So just as hard, ok, and was it clear what you, how clear, or how unclear was it what you had to do?

241 S: I'd say 3, because I got more confused.

242 [END DISCUSS TASK 83b]

243 [00:42:03]

244

245 R: Ok, great. A bar chart.

246 [BEGIN TASK 90]

247 [00:42:10]

248 S: [silence for 25 seconds] Ok. Hmm... Well, to print the bars, I would need a, also a loop, that runs the amount of times that says in each element, so I would need first to iterate through the values, and inside of it, another, a nested loop that prints the bar. [silence for 7 seconds] For the other one, I just, I don't need to know the index, so I would use a for each. [silence for 30 seconds] And for the other one... I would use a... for-loop... [silence for 40 seconds] So, it would be just the asterisk...

249 R: Above the k, yeah.

250 S: So for each value you print the amount of asterisks, and then you... you just go to the other... Ehm.. Think that's it. Or not... Each value in the values... You get the number which is value... And you print the asterisks.. Then you put the... I think that's it.

251 [END TASK 90]

252 [00:46:01]

253

254 [BEGIN DISCUSS TASK 90]

255

256 R: Ok. And we'll go to the survey part. If you look at your programme code, how complex do you find it, the algorithm?

257 S: Let's see. 3.

258 R: And the concepts?

259 S: Hmm... 4.

260 R: And did you know what you had to do?

261 S: Yeah.

262

263 [00:46:39]

264

265 R: Ok. What made this one different than the ones we've seen?

266 S: It was easier to imagine it with, like, thinking about the structures. Like, ok, I need to iterate with a loop for this [the array] and then with a loop for the bar. Thinking about the problems in terms of the structures maybe made it easier because there's, like, they're already defined to do exactly that, so.

267 R: Ok. You used two different for-loops. Was there a reason for that?

268 S: Hmm... Yeah, I ... Yeah. Well for the for each, I used it, because I don't do, keep track of the index, and for the other one, I need to keep track of the index because, because there are no elements in an integer, so we'd run it as many times as the value says.

269

270 [00:48:03]

271

272 R: Ok. And, if I give you this, where would you order it, where would you place it?

273 S: [silence for 15 seconds] I'd say, here.

274 R: Ok, you put the most difficult on top? So now you're saying that it's easier than the for-each-loop? We're finding the, what was this, counting zeroes.

275 S: Well, it felt easier, because it was quicker to imagine.

276 R: So, the fact that there's a for in the for doesn't mean it's harder than an if in a for? Actually, you find this one more difficult.

277 S: Maybe more time to understand it, or no.

278 R: No, could be yeah. I'm trying to figure out, what makes this one, what makes this one seem more complex than that one? What is the difference between those, what makes you give that, what makes you have that idea? Why do you have that feeling?

279 S: [silence for 20 seconds] Maybe it's about the variable.

280 R: The current?

281 S: Yeah, cause for me, like, the more variables there are, the more I need to think about the interactions. So... Yeah, this one was pretty straightforward, so....

282 [END DISCUSS 90]

283 [00:50:05]

284

285 R: Yeah, ok. Ok, great. Can we do one more, or are you tired? Ok, one last one. Ehm, there's the explanation here and under are two pieces of code. You can choose which one you want to copy-paste. Ok, so it looks longer, but this is just code or you use an array or an ArrayList. So feel free to scroll through that.

286 [00:50:32]

287 [START TASK 88]

288 S: [silence for 70 seconds]

289

290 [00:51:38]

291

292 R: So what are you thinking about?

293 S: Ehm... I guess merging them is easier for the ArrayList, because I don't need to, to know the size from the beginning. But... Yeah, I'm gonna go for ArrayList, because I can, I don't need to keep track of the index in the ArrayList.

294 R: Then you can just copy-paste that code.

295 S: Is this everything? [silence for 25 seconds] Ehm... Hmm... [silence for 20 seconds] You can use, ehm... [silence for 10 seconds] I need to keep track of the index for, but it can be the same for, for both ArrayLists, so, I'm imagining like a body which you had from the first list, you had from the second list and then you increase the index. Ehm... I'm gonna use a for-loop. [silence for 20 seconds] Can I use the size for the first one. So you, ehm, do the merged one, you... [mumbles] add index i, the first one... Yep, and then it's just copy-paste for the second one. And you... Yeah, and you don't need to... And I, I guess that's it.

296

297 [END TASK 88]

298 [00:55:50]

299

300 [START DISCUSS 88]

301 R: Ok. Then we go to the questions again. Merging rain lists, if you look at the code that you wrote there, how complex is it?

302 S: [silence for 15 seconds] Maybe 3.

303 R: And why did you choose 3?

304 S: Because again, like, the last one was, once you understand what you need to know, it's easier to, to understand how your structures are gonna, like, how you need to use the structures to, to do what you want to do, and that way it's just easier

Feb. 222 Variable Interactivity (effecting each other)
Jan 10, 2024 11:28 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O6 considers/knows construct - plan combo
Jan 10, 2024 11:29 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S2: FOR understandable
Jan 6, 2024 3:02 PM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S26 Simultaneous: (i.e. for multiple parameters)
Jan 10, 2024 11:30 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O7 tangled/patchwork
Jan 10, 2024 11:38 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O4NEG recalls familiar plan
Jan 10, 2024 11:39 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O6 considers/knows construct - plan combo
Jan 10, 2024 11:39 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S9 nested loops easy
Jan 10, 2024 11:40 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: O6 considers/knows construct - plan combo
Jan 10, 2024 11:40 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S22 variable interactivity (effecting each other)
Jan 10, 2024 11:41 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S18 nested conditional hard (harder than nested loop)
Jan 10, 2024 11:41 AM • Edit
Hit Enter to reply

Resolve Reply

You: S1 construct familiarity